

QUINOLINE-8-CARBOXYLIC ACID AS AN ANALYTICAL REAGENT. PART II

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In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 419) it was shown that quinoline-8-carboxylic acid can be used as a reagent for the estimation of copper between p_n 2.78 and 7.0, copper being completely precipitated. In presence of acetic acid, however, it was found that good results were obtained either by adding a few grams of sodium acetate, or a large excess of the sodium salt of the reagent, as the copper salt of quinoline-8-carboxylic acid was found like copper quinaldinate (Majumdar, *Analyst*, 1939, 64, 874; 1943, 68, 242) to show specific solubility in acetic acid, independent of p_n . In presence of mineral acid at a lower p_n value copper is completely precipitated but in presence of acetic acid even at a higher p_n the precipitation is incomplete.

It has now been found that cadmium and iron (ous) also form salts of similar composition as that of copper. On adding sodium salt of the reagent to a well cooled solution of ferrous salt containing Rochelle salt or hydroxylamine hydrochloride, a red colouration (pale red to dark red depending upon the concentration of iron) is obtained, the intensity of which increases with the addition of potassium cyanide. The colour given by quinaldinate acid under similar condition is, however, more intense; moreover, quinoline-8-carboxylic acid gives only a red compound and no *cis-trans* isomers (*cf.* Ray and Bose, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, 95, 400).

Using sodium salt of the reagent it is found that copper can be separated from arsenic, antimony, and bismuth in presence of Rochelle salt and also from cobalt and zinc in weakly acid solution. The results of these experiments are given below.

EXPERIMENTAL

Salts of Quinoline-8-carboxylic Acid

Cadmium Salt.—To an acid solution of cadmium salt was added an excess of a solution of sodium salt of the reagent. The cold solution was neutralised with dilute caustic soda solution till just alkaline (using bromothymol blue indicator). The precipitate which separated on stirring was filtered, washed with cold water and dried at 110°. On analysis the salt was found to contain 25% of cadmium and 5.8% of nitrogen (micro analysis). The compound $(C_{10}H_8O_2N)_2Cd$ requires 24.6% of cadmium and 6.1% of nitrogen.

Ferrous Salt.—On adding an excess of a solution of sodium salt of the reagent to that of ferrous ammonium sulphate containing Rochelle salt a dark red solution was obtained. This on cooling overnight was found to give a violet-red crystalline precipitate which was filtered, washed with cold water, dried in air and analysed. [Found : N (micro analysis), 6.73; Fe, 13.2. The compound $(C_{10}H_8O_2N)_2Fe \cdot H_2O$ requires N, 6.7; Fe, 13.4 per cent].

Separation of Copper from Arsenic, Antimony, Bismuth, Cobalt and Zinc.—To a solution of copper containing arsenic, antimony or bismuth a few grams of

Rochelle salt (2-4 g.) were added. The mixture was neutralised (using bromothymol blue indicator) and treated with a few c.c. of *N/10*- sulphuric acid. To the solution after dilution an excess of sodium salt of the reagent (1 g. of quinoline-8-carboxylic acid per 100 c.c. solution) was added with stirring. After cooling the precipitate was filtered through a gooch crucible, washed with cold water, dried at 150° and weighed.

In presence of cobalt or zinc, copper was estimated in the same way except that no Rochelle salt was added and the solution was heated to boiling both before and after the addition of the reagent. This was then quickly cooled with stirring, and the precipitate was filtered.

TABLE I

Weight of copper used = 0.01907 g.

Other metals.	<i>N/10</i> -H ₂ SO ₄ .	Reagent.	Total vol.	Weight of copper.		Error
				ppt.	found	
0.105 g. As	4 c.c.	20 c.c.	150 c.c.	0.1221 g.	0.01903 g.	-0.00004 g.
0.0105 "	5	20	150	0.1223	0.01906	-0.00001
0.042 "	5	20	150	0.1226	0.01911	0.00004
0.021 "	7	20	150	0.1221	0.01903	-0.00004
0.0521 Bi	4	20	150	0.1222	0.01905	-0.00002
0.1042 "	4	20	150	0.1225	0.01909	0.00002
0.1563 "	5	20	150	0.1224	0.01908	0.00001
0.3084 "	5	20	150	0.1229	0.01915	0.00008
0.0510 Sb	4	20	150	0.1226	0.01911	0.00004
0.1020 "	4	20	150	0.1222	0.01905	-0.00002
0.1530 "	5	20	150	0.1226	0.01911	0.00004
0.0285 Co	7	25	150	0.1227	0.01913	0.00006
0.0570 "	7	25	150	0.1230	0.01917	0.00010
0.0570 "	10	25	300	0.1222	0.01905	-0.00002
0.3018 Zn	10	25	300	0.1229	0.01915	0.00008
0.1509 "	10	25	300	0.1227	0.01913	0.00006

The copper solution and the solution of the reagent used in the above series of experiments were the same as was used in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 419), and all other reagents and chemicals used were of "pro-analyse" variety of Kahlbaum.

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